

Effect of Small-Scale Agribusiness Characteristics on the Utilization of Financial Records in Nasarawa State, Nigeria

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 26th Nov 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Small-scale Enterprise Agribusiness Financial Records</p>	<p>The study investigates the effect of small-scale agribusiness enterprise characteristics on the utilization of financial records in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. Specifically the study described the characteristics of the agribusiness enterprises, determine the effect of enterprise characteristics on financial records utilization and to examine the challenges of utilizing financial records. One hundred and thirty eight (138) small-scale agribusiness enterprises were selected through multi-stage and purposive sampling procedure and a well structure questionnaire was used to collect primary data. Simple percentage, multiple regression as well as factor analysis were utilized to analyze the data. The finding revealed that, majority (98.6%) of the enterprises were private owned while few (1.4%) were public owned with most of them (32.6%) into processing. It was also observed that majority of the enterprises (82.6%) were registered but majority do not have access to credit facilities (52.9%). The annual income of the enterprises shows a mean income of (₦4,036,958.52). It was also observed that majority of the enterprises utilized financial records for the purpose of profit margin determination and cost control. The result of multiple regression shows that years in business, level of income and competent employees were the major determinants of the choice and utilization of financial records keeping among agribusiness enterprises in the study area. The factors that hindered the utilization of financial records were accounting compliance factors, institutional and operational factors, financial and administrative factors, as well as economic and educational factors. It was recommended that agribusiness enterprises should seek basic knowledge of records keeping and hire the services of professionals for proper record keeping.</p>

1. Introduction

The term “Agribusiness” is an aspect of agriculture comprising of production, manufacturing and distribution of farm inputs, equipment and supplies at hand and the processing, storage and distribution of farm commodities on the other hand. This implies that the entire agricultural production, processing, distribution and consumption spectrum from farm inputs supplies inclusive of wood producers, furniture manufacturers, food processors, food packers, food transporters and food marketing companies to restaurants and shopping malls. It covers input industries for agricultural, production, post-farm gate industries; including the third party firms that facilitate agribusiness operations including bankers, brokers, advertising agencies and marketing information firms (Yumkella et al., 2021). In other words, agribusiness is the sum total of all the operations involved in the manufacture and distribution of farm supplies, production operations on the farms, storage-processing-distribution off-farm commodities and other items made from them. It is used as a combination of agriculture and business referring to the range of activities in modern food operations (Igbokwuwe et al., 2014).

According to Ura (2015), this documentation (financial record) is normally in the tradition form of records written down on paper; it may also be electronically kept on a computer, or both. A business has to keep records relating to all its transactions that are dated so that one can understand which records relate to what period. The types of records a business should keep include: Income statement (list of receipts and invoices), balance sheet, payroll, imports and exports schedules, contracts and agreements, bank statements, bills (like utility bills), stock records, asset register (list of assets) and many other documents or records relevant to the business such as debtors, credit and debit notes.

A similar view to that was given by Muchira (2012), who noted that agribusiness management involves proper record-keeping of transactions. Therefore, the key factors that positively influence the growth and sustainability of small scale enterprises are skills and knowledge in book-keeping. As opined by Germain (2009), poor recordkeeping of financial transactions leads to total collapse of businesses within few years of its establishment.

Effective financial record-keeping covering items such as invoices, receipts, bank statements and financial statements plays a vital role in promoting transparency, accountability, and informed decision-making. Poor financial records are a major growth barrier, leaving small-scale agribusiness enterprises vulnerable in hostile business environments (Hussein & Kühl, 2014). Without accurate financial records, small-scale agribusiness enterprises struggle to track performance, sales, profitability, and growth potential, which are essential for sustainability (Adeyemi & Akanji, 2020).

Globally, efficient financial records support business decisions regarding sales, inventory, marketing, and pricing (Ademola et al., 2012). Proper financial record-keeping ensures that small-scale agribusiness enterprises maintain positive cash flow, fulfill obligations, and remain competitive. By prioritizing financial records, small-scale agribusiness enterprises strengthen their financial health and contribute to Nigeria's economic resilience and development.

Financial record keeping is about the maintenance of history of one's activities, as financial dealings, by entering data in ledgers or journals, putting documents into files. The importance of financial record keeping can therefore not be overemphasized both in our contemporary lives and particularly in our businesses. From properly kept financial record a person can at any time ascertain: what property he possesses, what amount he owes and to whom, what profit he has made or what loss he has sustained for any given period and the manner in which the profit and loss has risen, and the amount of his capital or deficiency. If no records are kept, it will be difficult to find accurate net profit. Under such circumstances, tax authorities may overestimate the profits and thus a trader will suffer for not having kept the business records. In absence of proper business records, the trader will find it difficult to submit the true position to the court in case he becomes insolvent. Keeping of financial records help the agribusiness owners to make future plans and policies. Also, it will be difficult to ascertain and fix the price of business to be sold or disposed off if no records are kept. Finally, in spite of the best memory, it is beyond the capacity of agribusiness owners to remember all the business dealings with back references (Williams et al, 2008)

Globally, small-scale agribusiness enterprises have been acclaimed to play vital role in the economy of both developed and developing countries. About 75% of workforce in Europe consists of small-scale agribusiness enterprises (Rathnasiri, 2014).

In Nasarawa State, the performance of small scale agribusiness enterprise has continued to decline over years. According to Gok (2009), virtually most small scale agribusiness enterprise had collapsed leading to the closure of some of the small scale enterprise that were producing 40% of the employment in Nasarawa State. Other small scale enterprises were auctioned while some were merged or acquired signifying questionable financial performance due to lack of proper financial records keeping. Users of accounts include owners of the businesses, creditors, employees, investors, creditors, and relevant government agencies among others. In the light of the foregoing, this study assesses the impact of record keeping on the performance of small-scale agribusiness enterprise in Nasarawa State with a view to enhancing the continued operation and survival.

1.1 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to examine the effect of small-scale agribusiness characteristics on the utilization of financial records in the study area. However, the specific objectives include: Describe the characteristics of the agribusiness enterprises in the study area, determine the effect of enterprise characteristics on financial records utilization and to examine the challenges of utilizing financial records.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Decision Usefulness Theory

The decision usefulness theory was propounded by George J. Staubus, an accounting Professor in 1980. The theory states that the primary objective of financial reporting in any firm is to provide information that is useful in making investment decisions. Information is required at every stage of the decision making process. The quality of decision depends on the quality of information supplied and the improvements in the use of the information.

The basic assumption of decision usefulness theory is that the theory relied on individual motivation and cognition, and about the predictability of market behavior. The theory assumes that the choice of financial reporting is dependent on individual level of motivation and recognition. This assumption has call for criticism from researchers such as Paul and Sue (2014) Who opined that decision usefulness theory lacks the essential property that allows standard setters to rely on it at either the micro (individual decision-maker) level or the macro (economy-wide) level to justify the standards they issue. They conclude that as a rationale for regulation of financial reporting decision usefulness is incoherent and argued for a reconsideration of accountability for understanding accounting and for making investment decisions.

This theory emphasizes the relationship between proper financial records in effective decision making in small-scale agribusinesses which is based on such factors as timeliness, reliability, relevancy, materiality of the presented accounting data, understandability, comparability and verifiability (Ogunmola, 2017).

2.2 Agribusiness

Agribusiness is a broad concept that encompasses the various activities involved in the production, processing, marketing, and distribution of agricultural products and services. It represents the integration of agricultural production with other related industries such as processing, distribution, marketing, finance, and technology. Agribusiness is a complex and dynamic sector that encompasses a wide range of activities, stakeholders, and value chains. It plays a vital role in food production, economic development, and rural livelihoods, contributing to food security, poverty reduction, and sustainable agriculture globally.

According to Van-Eerd, (2019), agribusiness involves the conversion of raw agricultural commodities into value-added products through activities such as milling, refining, canning, packaging, and preserving. Rushton (2014) Agribusiness encompasses the distribution and logistics of agricultural products from farms and processing facilities to consumers. This includes transportation,

warehousing, and distribution networks. Agribusiness includes financial services such as credit, insurance, investment, and risk management designed to support farmers, agribusinesses, and rural communities. It also embraces technological advancements and innovations to improve agricultural productivity, sustainability, and efficiency. Srinivasan (2017).

2.3 Small-scale Enterprise

Generally, there is no consensus on the definition or nature of small and medium scale enterprises worldwide. According to Salako (2015), globally, the definition of Small and medium scale enterprises varies from country to country, depending on the parameters considered best suitable to promote the sub-sector in each country. Different countries, institutions and individuals have put forwards various descriptions of a small businesses based on some parameters. Oshogbemi (1983) and Ayozie (2013) major requirement for any successful business is to have well planned organization which sets down the various functions that must be performed. The structure also outline the responsibilities of all person associated with the enterprise, infact many small scale industries have no clear features although some of these businesses do have. For instance the features of small and medium scale enterprises in Nigeria are below listed; the owner must rate himself for success in business, nature of the business, the size of the enterprises, and evaluation of capital equipment, seek professional guidance and knowledge, and consider government regulation and source of raw materials.

Furthermore, Akinyande (2015) highlighted the definitions of small and medium scale enterprises by different institutions in Nigeria as follows: The Federal Ministry of Industry defines small-scale enterprise as the one having asset value of not more than N50million, with not more than 100 workers. The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) defines small-scale enterprise as the one having asset value of not more than N2million, with not more than 50 workers. The Association of Small and Medium Enterprises defines small-scale enterprise as the one having asset value of not more than 50million, with turnover of not more than N50million, having not more than 50 workers.

From the foregoing discussions, for the purpose of this study, small scale enterprises are defined as the one with asset value of not more than N5million, with turnover of not more than N15million, and having not more than 50 workers. Also, the researcher is of the view that what is common to the wide range of information available on the features of small scale enterprises is that the operations in the sector are usually in small scale; that production technique is labor intensive and that ownership is usually private. In most cases the workers in this sector are family members, apprentices and few paid employees.

3. Methodology

3.1 Study Area

The study was carried out in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. Nasarawa state is in the North Central region of Nigeria, bordered to the east by the states of Taraba and Plateau, to the north by Kaduna State, to the south by the States of Benue and Kogi, and to the west by the Federal Capital Territory. The state was created from the west of Plateau State on 1 October 1996. The state has thirteen local government areas and its capital is Lafia, located in the east of the state, while a key economic Centre of the state is the Karu Urban Area suburbs of Abuja along the western border with the Federal capital territory (FCT). The State lies between Latitudes: $8^{\circ} 32'$ and $20^{\circ} 22'$ N and Longitudes: $7^{\circ} 42'$ and $29^{\circ} 56'$ E. Agriculture is the mainstay of Nasarawa State's economy with the production of a variety of cash crops throughout the year. It also contains various minerals such as salt, barite, and bauxite, which are mostly mined by artisanal miners. The State is largely based around agriculture, mainly of sesame, soybeans, groundnut, millet, maize, and yam crops. Other key industries are services, especially in urban areas, and the livestock herding and ranching of cattle, goats, and sheep.

The choice of Nasarawa as the study area was based on the premise that the state is one the major hub for agribusiness enterprises such as "rice production, garri processing, fish farming, storage etc" in North-Central Nigeria. The State shares boundary with the Federal Capital Territory Abuja.

Figure 1: The map of Nigeria showing Nasarawa the study State.

Source: National Space Research Development Agency, (NASRDA, 2013)

Figure 2: The map of Nasarawa State showing the study area.

Source: National Space Research Development Agency, (NASRDA, 2013)

3.2 Population of the Study

The population for this study comprises of 210 agribusiness enterprises registered with ministry of agriculture and water resources as at 2024.

3.3 Sample Size/Sampling Technique

Taro Yamane’s Statistical formula was used to determine the sample size while Bow Ley’s proportional allocation formula was used to distribute respondents for even collection of data. This is important to avoid bias in the data collection process.

Taro Yamane’s Statistical formula stated as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

n= Sample size

N= Estimated population

e= Error margin or level of significant which is 5% (0.05) for social science research.

N= 210

$$n = \frac{210}{1 + 210(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{210}{1 + 210(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{210}{1 + 0.525}$$

$$n = \frac{210}{1.525}$$

n=138

3.4 Variable Specification

Variables used in the study are;

Nature of enterprise: was measured using dummy variable (1= public 0= private)

Number of workers: was measured in numbers

Access to credit: was measured using dummy variable (1= access 0= No access)

Legal status: was measured using dummy variable (1= registered, 0=not registered)

Age of the business: was measured in years, it represents the number of years the business had existed

Annual income; was measured in Naira

Dependent variable: Financial Records

3.5 Model Specification

The Multiple Regression Model: The Multiple Regression Model for enterprise characteristics that influence the utilization of financial records as well as effect of the characteristics of enterprise on their revenue was used to achieve hypothesis (i and iii) and is specified as follows;

$$Y = a_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4 + b_5X_5 + b_6X_6 + b_7X_7 + b_8X_8 + b_9X_9 + b_{10}X_{10} \dots + b_nX_n + \mu_i \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$Y = \text{Financial records utilization} = \frac{\text{Number of adapted records}}{\text{Number of records available}}$$

a= constant

b₁-b_n = regression coefficients

X₁=Years in business (years)

X₂=Level of income (Naira)

X₃=Access to credit facilities (1= access 0= No access)

X₄ =Membership of cooperative (1=member 0= Non-member)

X₅=Adequate knowledge of financial records (1=Yes 0=No)

X₆ =Competent employees (1=Yes 0= No)

X₇= Legal Status. (1=registered 0=Not registered)

X₈=Extension contact (1=Yes 0=No)

μ_i = error term

The Factor Analysis: The factors analysis model was used to achieve the challenges of financial records utilization (objective v) and is specified as follows:

$$X_i = X_i = a_1F_1 + a_2F_2 + a_3F_3 + a_4F_4 + a_5F_5 + a_6F_6 + a_7F_7 + a_8F_8 + a_9F_9 + a_{10}F_{10} \dots + a_{11}F_{11} n + u \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Where;

X1 = Regulatory changes

X2 = Time consuming

X3 = High cost involved

X4 = Resistance to change

X5= Fraud

X6= Error and Omission

X7= Lack of Facilities.

X8= Tedious

X9= Fear of discouragement in case of loss

X10= Standardization of record keeping method

X11= Fear of Taxation

X12= Lack of retention policy

X13= Lack of consistency

X14= Unskilled account staff

X15= Knowledge of business owners

F₁-F₁₅=factors to be extracted

U= error term

a₁-a₁₅ = Factors to load

μ_i = part of variable X_i that cannot be explained by the factors

4. Findings

4.1 Characteristics of agribusiness enterprises

Table 1 shows the characteristics of small scale agribusiness enterprises in the study State. The findings on the nature of the enterprise revealed that majority (98.6%) of the enterprises were private owned while few (1.4%) were public. This implies that the agribusiness sector in the study area is largely dominated by private individuals. This can be attributed to the fact that small-scale agribusiness require little capital formation. This finding is in agreement with Nicolas (2017) who reported that small-scales are owned by one entrepreneur with little capital involvement. The finding on the type of agribusiness enterprise shows that most of the enterprises (32.6%) were into processing, while few (1.4%) were aggregators. The dominance of agribusiness enterprises in the processing activities is a sign that most of the agribusiness enterprises in the study area are more interested in value addition

which is an indicator of economic growth individual business and the country at large. This is in line with the findings of Aworh (2009) who reported that the agribusiness sector is dominated by food and agro-processing enterprises

The findings on the legal status show that majority of the agribusiness enterprises (82.6%) were registered, while (17.4%) were not registered. This implies that most of the enterprises by virtue of their registration have potentials to access credit facilities from financial institutions. This finding is in line with that of Akaa *et al.* (2024) who observed that for small scale agribusiness enterprises to access credit facilities from formal financial institutions, they must either registered with corporate affairs commission or are members of cooperative societies.

The finding on access to credit facilities shows that 47.1 % had access to credit facilities while 52.9% had no access to credit facilities. It can be deduced that even though most of the agribusiness enterprises in the study area are registered they still lack basic knowledge about credit availabilities. This finding is in agreement with that of Akaa *et al.* (2024) who found out that, majority of small scale agribusiness enterprises are ignorant and have difficulties in accessing various financing alternatives including leveraging on government programs to expand their scale of operations. This also supported the finding of international finance cooperation (IFC, 2019) that small scale agribusiness enterprise are less likely to be able to obtain bank loans than large enterprises, instead they rely on internal funds or cash from friends and family to launch and run their enterprises.

The findings on the number of workers indicated that majority (48.6%) of the enterprises had five (5) or less workers, 47.8% had 6-10 workers, while 3.6% had 11 workers and above, with a mean of 6.0 workers. It can be deduced that agribusiness enterprises in the area are largely small scale. This is in agreement with Mekwunye (2018) who asserted that small enterprises have between one and nine employees.

The findings on the years in business indicated that, majority (60.9%) had five (5) years or less, 28.3% had between 6 and 9 years of experience while 3.9% had 10 years and above. The mean years spent in the business was 5years which means that most of the small scale enterprises are in their infant stage and have opportunity for growth and expansion. Majority of the small-scale agribusiness in this study are young due to their response to these policies of government on SMEs such as funding, incentives and provision enabling environment. This is in consonance with Ogundele (2015) who reported that most small scale enterprises have an average existence of seven years.

The result on the annual income of the enterprise shows that 30.4% had annual income from ₦1,000,000 or less, 14.5% had annual income of ₦2,000,000 or less, 6.5% had annual income ₦3000000 or less, while majority (48.6%) had annual income of above ₦3,000,000. The mean annual income of the enterprises was found to be ₦4,036,958.52. This implies that small scale enterprises because of their scale of operation have small annual return. This finding is in line with that of Ayinde (2015) who noted that small scale enterprises usually have asset value of not more than ₦10million.

Table 1 Characteristics of the Enterprises (n= 138)

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
<i>Nature of enterprise</i>			
Private	136	98.6	
Public	2	1.4	
<i>Type of Agribusiness Enterprise</i>			
Production	38	27.5	
Processing	45	32.6	
Marketing	35	25.4	
Storage	18	13.0	
Assembling	2	1.4	
<i>Legal status</i>			
Registered	114	82.6	
Not registered	24	17.4	
<i>Access to credit facilities</i>			
Have access	65	47.1	
Do not have access	73	52.9	
<i>Number of workers (Number)</i>			6.00
≤ 5	67	48.6	
6-10	66	47.8	
≥11	5	3.6	
<i>Years in business (years)</i>			5.23
≤ 5	84	60.9	
6-9	39	28.3	
≥10	15	10.9	
<i>Annual income (₦)</i>			4,036,958.52
≤ 1,000,000	42	30.4	
1,100,000-2,000,000	20	14.5	
2,100,000-3,000,000	9	6.5	
>3,000,000	67	48.6	

Source: Research Data, 2025

4.2 Effect of enterprise characteristics on financial records utilization

Table 2 shows the influence of enterprise characteristics on the utilization of financial records. The multiple linear regression models was selected in the analysis of enterprise characteristics that influence the utilization of financial records in the study area. The findings indicated that (50.39%) of variation in the level of financial record utilization is occasion by the independents variables selected for the exponential regression model as indicated by the R². This implies that (49.61%) of variations in the utilization of financial record keeping by small scale agribusiness enterprises are caused by factors not captured in the model.

The F-Value (10.57) as indicated in table 4.4.1 is significant at (1%) level. This implies that the null hypothesis which states that enterprise characteristics do not significantly influence the utilization of financial records is therefore rejected. The coefficient of average income was positive but not significant conform to the *a priori* expectation that income level of small scale enterprises could be positive in terms of financial records utilization but statistically insignificant. This implies that as the income of small scale enterprises increases most of them becomes over confidence about record keeping not paying much attention. This is in consonance with the findings of Umar (2019) who noted that proper record keeping will bring more confidence on both the lenders and creditors of small scale enterprises.

The years in business which is significant at (1%) with negative coefficient implies that the years of enterprises significantly influence the utilization of financial records. The negative coefficient implies that newly established small scale agribusiness enterprises pay more attention to records of their business than matured enterprise. As the years of enterprise increases, utilization of financial records decreases by 1.03%. This is because as businesses mature, owners may become complacent and less diligent in maintaining accurate financial records thereby leading to less utilization. This is in line with the findings of Harley (2017) who reported that small business owners may not possess the necessary accounting expertise to maintain accurate financial records, leading to a decline in record-keeping over time.

The findings on membership of cooperative was positive (0.4267) and significant at 1%, this is possible because of the awareness created by the agribusiness cooperative societies through training and support to members on maintaining accurate and timely records. Cooperatives can also provide members with access to financial experts, helping them to better plan and manage their finances, promotes transparency in record keeping and reducing the risk of errors and mismanagement. This is in concord with the findings of Mwangi (2017) who provides evidence that cooperative membership can have a positive impact on financial record-keeping practices, which can, in turn, improve financial performance, access to credit, and financial literacy

The findings on how adequate knowledge of financial records influences the utilization of financial records was positive (0.250) and significant at 5%, this is because by having knowledge of financial records, individuals can unlock the full potential of financial record-keeping, making informed decisions, and achieving their financial goals. This is in line with Epstein and Jermakowicz (2010) who reported that by understanding financial statements, performing financial analysis, and ensuring accurate financial reporting and disclosure, users can make informed decisions and achieve their financial goals.

The findings on how legal status influence the utilization of financial records was positive (0.3698) and significant at 1%. This implies that registered small scale agribusiness are more likely to access credit facilities from financial institutions, as they are perceived as more stable and secure. It can also attract investors, as it provides a level of assurance about the business's legitimacy and financial transparency. This is in accordance with the findings of Epstein and Jermakowicz (2010) which reported that registered agribusiness can access quick formal financial services, such as loans and credit, which can help them grow and expand.

Table 2 Effect of enterprise characteristics on financial records utilization

Variable	Coefficient	Std error	t-value	P-value
Average income	6.80×10 ⁻⁹ NS	1.43×10 ⁻⁸	0.47	0.637
Years in business	-1.034124***	0.2763882	-3.74	0.000
Level of income	0.0414903 ^{NS}	0.2111873	0.20	0.845
Access to credit facilities	0.1369976 ^{NS}	0.1218037	1.12	0.264
Membership of cooperative	0.426657***	0.1337521	3.19	0.002
Adequate Knowledge of financial records	0.2504854**	0.0953115	2.63	0.011
Competent employees	-0.0478689 ^{NS}	0.0956146	-0.50	0.618
Legal status	0.3698491***	0.1044067	3.54	0.001
Extension service	-0.1539374 ^{NS}	0.1321408	-1.16	0.247
Constant	2.094555***	0.3748071	5.59	0.000
R-Square	0.5039			
Adjusted R-Square	0.4555			
F-value	10.57***			

Source: Research Data, 2025 ***, **, & *, sig@1%, 5% and 10% respectively, NS= not sig

4.3 Challenges to Utilization of Financial Records

Table 3 shows the challenges faced by small agribusiness enterprises in the utilization of financial records. Factor analysis was used to identify factors that constrain the utilization of financial records among agribusiness enterprises in the study area. Using Kaiser's normalization rule of thumb of 0.4 as a minimum point a variable will load before it can be accepted as having effect on the utilization of financial record. The study identified time consuming, fraud, fear of taxation, errors and omission, fear of discouragement in case of loss, tedious, Regulatory changes, unskilled account staff, Resistance to change, lack of finance, lack of consistency, lack of retention policy, high cost implication and knowledge of business owners.

The factors were categorized in to four major factors. The factors include accounting compliance factors, institutional and operational factors, financial and administrative factors, as well as economic and educational factors.

Based on the factors loaded the following accounting compliance factors were extracted: time consuming (0.717), fraud (0.793), and fear of taxation (0.438), error and omission (0.572). The accounting compliance challenges experience is in line with the finding of Amoako (2013) who asserted that time consuming and exposure of financial position, payment of taxes makes many small scale enterprises not to keep records because of difficult in maintain an accounting system.

The institutional and operational factors loaded include; fear of discouragement in case of loss (0.775), tedious (0.672), regulatory changes (0.573), unskilled account staff (0.813), resistance to change (0.764), standardization of record keeping (0.431). This reveal is in consonance with that of Ibrahim (2015) who noted that recruitment of incompetent accountants can lead to inaccurate record keeping. Okafor (2012) also observed that most owners of small scale enterprise sees their business as their private affairs therefore, there is no need to be accountable and transparent to anyone.

The financial and administrative constraints identified by the enterprises; lack of finance (0.752), lack of consistency (0.841), lack of retention policy (0.628) is in line with the findings of Musah and Ibrahim (2014) who observed that some small scale enterprises have the tendency of relying on their memory rather than keeping proper financial records thus becomes their mode of operation.

The economic and educational factors identified include high cost implication (0.772) and knowledge of the business owners (0.851). This implies that the technical knowledge of the business owners in understanding the basic tenants of financial records that can the utilization of financial records. This finding is in conformity with that of Onalapo and Adegbite (2014) who posited that lack of basic knowledge of business owners on records keeping makes them to employed unskilled accounts staff which eventually caused stagnation in business not knowing how business is performing and some eventually fold up.

Table 3: Challenges in the Utilization of Financial Records

Challenges	Accounting compliance factors	Institutional and operational factors	Financial and administrative factors	Economic and Educational factors
Time consuming	0.717			
fraud	0.793			
Fear of taxation	0.438			
Errors and omission	0.572			
Fear of discouragement in case of loss		0.775		
Tedious		0.672		
Regulatory changes		0.573		
Unskilled account staff		0.813		
Resistance to change		0.764		
Standardization of record keeping		0.431		
Lack of finance			0.752	
Lack of consistency			0.841	
Lack of retention policy			0.628	
High cost implication				0.772
Knowledge of business owners				0.851

Source: Research Data, 2025 *= significance based on Kaiser Normalization

5. Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Summary

This study examine the effect of small-scale agribusiness enterprise characteristics on the utilization of financial records in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to; described the characteristics of the agribusiness enterprises, determine the effect of enterprise characteristics on financial records utilization and to examine the challenges of utilizing financial records.

Results on the characteristics of small scale agribusiness enterprise revealed that majority (98.6%) of the enterprises were private owned while few (1.4%) were public owned. Majority of the enterprises (32.6%) were into processing, while few (1.4%) were aggregators, large number of the agribusiness enterprises (82.6%) were registered, while 17.4% were not registered and that (47.1%) have access to credit facilities while majority (52.9%) lack access to credit facilities. Majority (48.6%) of small scale agribusiness enterprises have five (5) or less workers, (47.8%) have 6-10 workers, while (3.6%) have 11 workers above, with a mean of (6) workers. On the basis of years in business, majority 60.9% have existed for about five (5) years or less, 28.3% have 6-9 years of experience while 3.9% have 10 years above. The mean years spend in the business was (5.23) and the annual income of the enterprise shows that 30.4% have annual income of ₦1,000,000 or less, 14.5% have annual income of ₦2,000,000 or less, 6.5% have income ₦3,000,000 or less, while majority (48.6%) have annual income of ₦3,000,000 and above with a mean income of ₦4,036,958.52.

It was also discovered that the mean incomes (₦4,873,076.92) of agribusiness enterprises that utilized financial records compared to those that do not utilized financial records.

The major challenges encountered by agribusiness enterprises in the utilization of financial records were knowledge of business owners (85.1%), lack of consistency (84.1%), unskilled account staff (81.3%), fraud (79.3%), fear of discouragement in case of

loss (77.5%), high cost implication, (77.2%), resistant to change (76.4%) lack of finance (75.2%) and time consuming (71.7%). Challenges with less severity were fear of taxation (43.8%) and standardization of record keeping (43.1%).

5.2 Conclusion

This study was carried out to examine the effect small-scale agribusiness enterprise characteristics on the utilization of financial records in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. It was discovered that majority of the enterprises were private owned, Majority of the enterprises were into processing activities, most of the agribusiness enterprises were registered and have access to credit facilities, majority of the enterprises have five (5) or less workers and have been existing for about five (5) years with a mean annual income of ₦4,036,958.52. It was also discovered that majority keep cash statement and inventory records and majority of the enterprises utilized financial records for the purpose of profit margin determination.

Results also show that nature of enterprise greatly influences the utilization of record keeping. The major challenges encountered by agribusiness enterprises in the utilization of financial records were knowledge of business owners, lack of consistency, unskilled account staff, fraud, fear of discouragement in case of loss, high cost implication, resistant to change, lack of finance and time consuming.

Based on the findings of this research it can be deduced that, financial records play a vital role in the income of small scale agribusiness enterprises. From the empirical analysis, it was discovered that bookkeeping is very key to successful running of small scale agribusiness enterprises to achieve better performance in revenue generation and profit making. Also for small scale agribusiness enterprises who aimed at making profit and achieving greater performance record keeping is indispensable and must be kept with all level of professionalism for optimal results.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this research, the following recommendations were made.

- Small scale agribusiness owners should seek for basic financial records knowledge to enable them keep records of business transactions properly.
- Small scale agribusiness enterprises should engage the services of Professionals who will be able to keep proper records and prepare relevant financial report at a minimal cost for the business
- Governments and financial institutions should initiate financial literacy programs to educate small scale agribusiness owners on how to manage their finances and access credit facilities.
- There should be adequate sensitization in form of seminars and workshops from the relevant Accounting professional bodies such as ANAN, ICAN, and CITN to increase the awareness of importance of operating good financial records system to this sector so that they can achieve their objectives.

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